

Studies On the Seasonal Variation in Primary Productivity in Millat Nagar Wetlands of Kamwari River, Bhiwandi, District Thane, Maharashtra

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Abstract:

Primary productivity provides information about the amount of energy available to support the system's bioactivities. The present study has been carried out to study the seasonal variation in primary productivity in Millat Nagar Wetlands of the Kamwari river of Bhiwandi city, Maharashtra. Monthly data for primary productivity was collected by using light and dark bottle technique of Gaarder and Gran (1927) as mentioned in Trivedy and Goel (1986). The dissolved oxygen was analyzed by Winkler's method with azide modification (APHA, 2005), in every month for a period of one year (1st January 2019 to 31st December 2019). The maximum average Gross primary productivity was observed in pre-monsoon 85.55mgC/m³/hr and minimum in monsoon 54.84mgC/m³/hr. The NPP was observed maximum in pre-monsoon 49.86mgC/m³/hr and minimum in monsoon 34.96 mgC/m³/hr, season of the study period.

Keywords – GPP, NPP, Primary Productivity, Millat Nagar Wetlands, Kamwari River, Seasonal Variation.

Introduction:

The primary productivity of an ecosystem is the rate at which solar radiation is store in the form of organic matter by producer species by photosynthetic and chemosynthetic processes, which are consumed as food materials at various trophic levels. It provides information about the amount of energy available to support the systems bioactivity in an aquatic realm (Vollenweider, 1969).). Thus, it helps to understand the food chain and food web relationship that prevails in the ecosystem. In natural waters, primary production almost entirely depends upon photosynthesis. The primary production in fresh water ecosystem mostly relies on phytoplankton and macrophytes. The phytoplankton is universal in occurrence and accounts for maximum productivity in the wetland ecosystem. The planktonic primary production provides the base upon which the aquatic food chain culminates. At the same time it generates about 70% of world's

atmospheric oxygen supply (Reynolds, 1984). The unique feature of wetlands is the inhabitation of planktonic organisms considered as index of fertility of the habitat (Fraser, 1962). Further, the primary productivity of any ecosystem is also regarded as the rate at which the biomass is produced per unit area by plant organisms. The biomass is used by consumers of the food chain of the system. The base of ecosystem functioning is the biological production of autotrophs which is manipulated by primary productivity of a water body (Mohanty et al., 2014; Odum et al., 1971). There is a main role of primary productivity in providing energy and organic matters to the entire biological community (Ahmed et al., 2005). Primary productivity at each level can be distinguished further into gross primary production i. e the total amount of organic matters produced and net primary production or the amount of organic matter produced of a particular level (Sheikh Nissar and Yeragi, 2003).

The aquatic bodies have been till date the potential source of organic production for the whole living organisms. Study on primary productivity in the freshwater ecosystems was reported by Harilal (2005), and Baber and Raje (2015). The present study has been undertaken to analyse the seasonal variation of Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) and Net Primary Productivity (NPP) in wetlands of Kamwari river Bhiwandi. Dist.Thane, Maharashtra.

Materials And Methods:

Study area: Geographically Millat Nagar (19.31471600N 73.06977300E) is a locality in Bhiwandi city. Its average elevation from the mean sea level is 26 m. This perennial freshwater wetland is located in Millat Nagar, Bhiwandi. The Millat Nagar wetland is a freshwater wetland, the wetlands are of swamps and marshes types. The wetland is surrounded by villages, grazing fields, agricultural fields and wetlands. Most of the neighbouring people are dependent on wetlands resources directly or indirectly. The major source of water to the wetland is rainwater from its catchment area during monsoon season and river water flowing beside the wetland also receiving water by flowing down the rainwater from surrounding areas during monsoon season.

To study the seasonal variation in primary productivity in Millat Nagar Wetlands of the Kamwari river, monthly data for primary productivity was collected by using light and dark bottle technique of Gaarder and Gran (1917) as mentioned in Trivedy and Goel (1986). The dissolved oxygen was analyzed by Winkler's method with azide modification (APHA, 2005).

Further GPP and NPP were calculated as follows:

$$GPP = \frac{L-D}{T} * \frac{0.375}{PQ} * 1000 \text{ mg C/m}^3/\text{hr}$$

$$NPP = \frac{L-I}{T} * \frac{0.375}{PQ} * 1000 \text{ mg C/m}^3/\text{hr}$$

Where, L= Light bottle, D= Dark bottle, I= Initial bottle, PQ= Photosynthetic quotient= 1.2

Arrow in the map showing sampling sites

Fig.1: Satellite location of Millat Nagar Wetlands, Kamwari river, Bhiwandi, Dist. Thane, Maharashtra.

Result:

In the present study, primary productivity of Millat Nagar Wetlands, Kamwari river has been calculated. Seasonal variations in primary productivity were observed as Gross primary productivity, Net primary productivity from 1st January 2019 to 31st December 2019 is depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Seasonal variation of Primary Productivity (mgC/m³/hr) of Millat Nagar Wetlands, Kamwari river from 1st January 2019 to 31st December 2019

Seasons	Average GPP	Average NPP
Pre monsoon	85.55	49.86
Monsoon	54.84	34.96
post monsoon	76.55	36.15

Abbreviation: GPP = Gross Primary Productivity, NPP= Net Primary Productivity,

Fig. 2: Seasonal variation of Primary Productivity ($\text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$) of Millat Nagar Wetlands, Kamwari river from 1st January 2019 to 31st December 2019

Gross primary productivity: The maximum average Gross primary productivity was recorded in pre-monsoon $85.55 \text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$ and minimum in monsoon $54.84 \text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$,

Net primary productivity: The maximum average Net primary productivity was recorded in pre-monsoon $49.86 \text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$ and minimum in monsoon $34.96 \text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{hr}$.

Discussion:

The primary productivity of any ecological system is the rate at which the biomass is produced per unit area by plants, the primary producers. It is the rate at which sun's radiant energy is stored by Photosynthetic activities of producer organisms in the form of organic substances which can be used as food material. In the present study, the seasonal variation of Gross Primary Productivity (GPP) and Net Primary Productivity (NPP) of the wetlands were assessed to understand the functioning of these wetland ecosystems.

The variation in Gross primary productivity was recorded that the minimum Gross primary productivity and Net primary productivity was observed in monsoon period, while the high value of Gross primary productivity and Net primary productivity was observed in post monsoon season. Similar observation was recorded by patil and Chavan (2010) while studying primary productivity

studies in some freshwater reservoirs of Sangli District, Maharashtra, they selected aquatic bodies namely Bhambarde, Lengre and Atpadi for their primary productivity studies. The Gross primary productivity of Bhambarde reservoir differs from 1.49 to $5.14 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$. The maximum value of Gross primary productivity $5.14 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ was found in pre-monsoon, and the minimum value $1.49 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ in monsoon. At Lengre reservoir, Gross primary productivity value fluctuated from 1.56 to $5.28 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$ with the maximum value in pre-monsoon, and the minimum value in monsoon. Atpadi reservoir shows Gross primary productivity value ranging from 1.31 to $4.98 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$. In this reservoir they noted Gross primary productivity increases in the pre-monsoon season and decreases in the monsoon season. The Net primary productivity value at Bhambarde reservoir varied from 1.31 to $3.27 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$. The maximum value was recorded in pre monsoon, and the minimum value was in the monsoon season. The Net primary productivity values at Lengre reservoir ranged between 1.18 to $3.43 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$. At Atpadi reservoir Net primary productivity values differ from 1.18 to $2.51 \text{O}_2 \text{mg}/\text{L}/\text{h}$. In both the reservoirs the maximum Net primary productivity values were recorded in pre-monsoon season, and the minimum values were recorded in the monsoon season.

Mandal et al., (2005) also recorded the Gross and Net primary productivity fluctuating to increase from late winter and reaching peak in the late summer in Karwar lake, Bihar. Synudeen Sahib (2002) reported that the maximum value of Gross primary productivity and Net primary productivity are in pre-monsoon season at Parapper reservoir of Kollam district in Kerala. Similar results were recorded by Hujare et al., (2007) in two perennial tanks from Kolhapur district. They noted maximum values of Gross primary productivity and Net primary productivity in pre-monsoon season, and minimum values in monsoon season.

In the present investigation the productivity increased from post-monsoon and attains the peak in pre-monsoon and then declines in monsoon season.

The productivity depends on the availability of nutrients. The maximum values of primary productivity during pre-monsoon may be due to intensive sunlight with high temperature and phytoplankton diversity with presence of nutrients whereas low productivity during monsoon season could be attributed to the reduced photo period coupled with low light intensity, temperature, dilution of nutrients and reduced phytoplankton.

Conclusion:

Wetlands primary productivity varies greatly due to diverse conditions. It is also a vital indicator for assessing wetland function, pollution levels and climate effect.

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